

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF TENSE CLAUSES IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

No extensive scientific study of tense clauses in English has been conducted so far. Time branch sentences are a special and important part of the vocabulary of the language. The development of this topic, dedicated to the semantic-grammatical analysis of verbs and tenses based on English language materials, stems from the lack of research in this field and the serious need to describe the composition of the tense form of verbs in English in a wide and comprehensive manner. A separate research paper has not been written about tense sentences, and their main semantic and grammatical features have not been studied in depth. It should be noted that the number of both simple and complex verbs is large for the formation of tense sentences. The fact that several tense verbs follow each other in a time branch sentence and examine other tenses in a form that is appropriate in terms of meaning allows to determine the regularities of the English language in that direction and helps to get a correct idea of the semantic development of its lexical system. At the same time, the detailed study of the verbs that indicate the time of the entire action lays the groundwork for the study of combinations formed with the help of verbs from other lexical-semantic groups. The main aspect that characterizes the grammatical structure of the modern English language and distinguishes it from the grammatical structure of the modern Azerbaijani language is its inherent analyticity. The main goal of the article is to study in detail the grammatical features of English tenses and compare them with Azerbaijani tenses, to reveal similarities and differences. It is also to study the lexical-semantic and modality characteristics of the tense forms of verbs in English, to determine the meaning and grammatical relations of those verbs. Students and translators encounter many difficulties in teaching and translating tense sentences. In our opinion, that research work is to make a certain contribution to the development of our linguistics. In the article, the lexical-semantic features of tense sentences in modern English, as well as grammatical-categorical features are defined. The generalizations obtained here and the proposed propositions can be used in future works related to the syntax of the English language as well as general linguistics. As for the practical importance of the work, the results of the dissertation can be used in the lectures on general-theoretical, as well as comparative and typological linguistics courses taught in the philology faculties of higher schools, in the methodology of teaching English grammar in the Azerbaijani student audience, in the theory and practice of translation, as well as in the subordinate complex sentence for higher and secondary schools. can be used in the preparation of textbooks and methodical materials on syntax.

Keywords: time branch sentences, semantic development, verbs.

In modern English, most of the tense forms are formed by auxiliary verbs: the present and past continuous forms of the auxiliary verb to be (1), the present and past perfect forms of the auxiliary verb to have (2), the indefinite form of the future tense shall/will auxiliary verbs (3), the auxiliary verbs shall/will and to be in the future tense (4), the auxiliary verbs to have and to be in the present and past continuous forms (5), and the future tense form shall/will, to have and to be are made using auxiliary verbs (6), for example: 1) I am speaking when you are at class. 2) When I was a child, he left his house 5 years ago. 3) We shall go, until I am hungry. 4) I shall be working, while the child sleeps in the room. 5) We have been working on this article on this information, before its late date. 6) I shall have been working but except for me, none will be here tomorrow. There are many more examples of grammatical meanings expressed in this way in modern English. It is clear from here that the main aspect that forms the general picture of the modern English grammatical structure is indeed analyticalism. It should be noted that the English language has not always been as poor as it is today in terms of morphological-synthetic form. Old English (500-1100 AD) had a rich and complex system of synthetic forms. In this period, the noun had the categories of

grammatical gender, case and quantity: three grammatical genders of the noun (masculine, feminine and middle) and four cases (nominative, possessive, effective and directional) [25, p.58]. Suffixes existed in Old English to indicate every gender and case. During the Middle English period (1100s and 1500s), a number of synthetic forms unique to English resulted from a series of events that occurred during the Middle English period (1100s and 1500s), especially the phonetic phenomenon called The Great Vowel Shift. started and then went out of use and disappeared.

In English, there are four tenses of the news form of the verb, which differ in both formation and processing:

1st group - simple (indefinite) time forms (Simple Tenses);

2nd group - continuous tenses (Continuous Tenses);

3rd group - perfect tenses;

Group 4 - Perfect Continuous Tenses.

When translating or working with tense clause forms, it is useful to observe the following sequence.

1. It is necessary to pay attention to the use of the tense form, that is, to the category of verbs, to determine whether the action will continue, whether it will continue or end.

2. What form the main verb should be or which auxiliary verb should be used will inform the correction of the time branch sentence form, that is, in the correction of the determined time form.

3. Attention should be paid to the presence of indefinite time adverbs required by the tense branch sentence form and their correct use. In English, there are adverbs of time that express the manner of the action and determine which tense form to use.

4. At that time, the question and negative forms of the affirmative sentence in the form of a branch sentence should be controlled. Question and negative sentences are formed with an auxiliary verb in the function of a news suffix. If there is no auxiliary verb in the sentence, the question and negative 4 forms of that sentence are formed only with the auxiliary verb "to do". In English, there are only two tenses without an auxiliary verb: present and past indefinite tenses (if the message of the sentence is expressed by the main verb) [32, p.125].

In complex sentences with subordinate clauses of time or condition, if, till, when, until, before, after, as soon as, as long as, unless, provided that, after the conjunctions, although the action is future, the verb is used in the simple present tense form. In complex subordinate clauses with complete branch clauses, the simple future tense form can be used after the conjunctions if, when. I shall go for a walk if he comes. If he comes, I will go for a walk. We will tell them everything when they return. We will tell them everything when they return.

The role of these time adverbs in the formation of tense sentences is great: yesterday, the day before yesterday, last week/month, last, two weeks (days, months) ago to express past actions with time adverbs such as two weeks/day, month/ago, in 2010 (in 2010), in one's childhood (in childhood), etc.; She finished school last year. He finished school last year. I saw your brother two days ago. I saw your brother 2 days ago. - The time when the action took place can also be indicated by a branch sentence in the past tense. I lived in Turkey when I studied at the University. I lived in Turkey when I studied at the university. To express successive actions in the past; He entered the room, sat at the table, began to look through the papers. He went in, sat down at the table, and started looking through the newspapers.

Tomorrow, the day after tomorrow, next week (month, year), in two (three) days, etc., to indicate actions that will happen or be performed in the future. time adverbs are used in tense clauses. In our language, depending on the meaning, the future tense is translated with definite and indefinite forms. She will be a student next year. He will be a student next year. I shall take the book from the library tomorrow. I will take the book from the library tomorrow.

Present Simple is used instead of Future Simple in tense sentences to indicate an action that will happen in the future. I will go to school when the rain stops. When it stops raining, I will go to school. When the wind stops, we will play football. When the wind dies down, we will play football. If you help me, I will finish my work in time.

A subordinate clause is a syntactically dependent part of a complex sentence, connected by a conjunction, explaining the main sentence, expressing the same idea.

There are two types of complex sentences in English.

1. Complex Sentences and Compound Sentences.

2. An independent complex sentence consists of equal simple sentences that do not depend on each other. In turn, a subordinate complex sentence consists of unequal sentences, where one of them explains the other [3, p.42].

The clause that explains another sentence is called the Subordinate Clause. The clause explained by the subordinate clause is called the Principal Clause.

In a complex sentence, the subordinate clause performs the function of one of the sentence members: the subject, the nominal part of the complex predicate, the complement, the determiner and the condition.

Complex sentences usually answer questions answered by members of a simple sentence and are extended members of a simple sentence.

There are as many types of subordinate clauses as the number of sentence members [5, p. 158].

Subject. Subordinate complex sentence, subject.

What is interesting? This film is interesting. What you say is interesting.

The nominal part of the predicate. An adverbial clause is a predicate.

What is the ease? The easiest is to pay it in time. The easy is whether we will be able to pay it in time.

Direct addition. An additional subordinate clause that corresponds to the direct object.

What did he show them? He showed them a story. He showed them what he had told there.

Preposition indirect object. An additional subordinate clause that corresponds to the indirect object.

What was he thankful for? He was grateful for their help. He was thankful for what they had done for him.

Set. Identify the clause.

What journal have you bought? I have bought an illustrated journal. I have bought a journal which is illustrated with interesting pictures.

Adverb clause

When did you call him? I called him yesterday. I called him when I was at the market.

Subject Clauses.

In a complex sentence, subordinate clauses perform the function of subject and who?, what? answers their questions. They are connected to the main clause with the conjunctions that, whether, if and the conjunctions who (whom), whose, what, which, when, where, how, why.

That he has made a mistake is strange. Whether they will come today is not known yet.

When a branch sentence begins with the conjunction whether, the translation of such a sentence begins with the particle li corresponding to the conjunction whether after the verb.

Branch clauses, subjects often follow the predicate; in this case, the pronoun dog comes before the

predicate. For example: It is strange that he has made a mistake. It is uncertain when we shall start [1, p.97].

Branch clauses are not separated from the main clause by commas.

The Predicative Clause.

Predicative branch clauses perform the function of the nominal part of the compound predicate in a compound sentence and what? how is it answers questions such as They are connected to the main clause with the same conjunctions and conjunctions as the branch clause.

For example:

The problem is that I have lost her address.

The verb closed before the predicative branch sentences is often translated into Azerbaijani by the following words: to is composed; consists of

The question is whether they will be able to help us.

The predicative branch clause is not separated from the main clause by a comma.

Object Clauses.

In a complex sentence, the complete branch clause functions as a direct or prepositional object. What? about what? for what? answers their questions. They are connected to the main clause by the same conjunctions and conjunctions as predicative and predicative branch clauses. For example: They laughed at what he said. He has just gone away saying that he will return in an hour.

A complete branch clause is not separated from the main clause by a comma.

Attributive Clauses.

Determinative clauses perform the determining function in a complex sentence and what? which? answers their questions. They are connected with the main clause by the following allied words: who (whom), whose, which, that pronouns and when, where, why adverbs.

The man who was here yesterday is a painter. Our representative, whose letter I showed you yesterday, will return at the end of the week.

There are three types of definite article:

1. Personalization that serves as a personal sign of a person or object, for example: The children who live in that house are my son's friends.

2. A classification that serves as a sign that a person or object belongs to any class of person or object: Children who live by the sea usually begin to swim at an early age.

3. A description that serves to describe a person or an object or to provide additional information about it: In the street I met some children, who showed me the way to the station [5, p.147].

Adverbial Clauses.

Conditional clauses function as different cases in a complex sentence. According to their meaning, they are divided into the following: Conditional branch sentences: time, place, cause, result, action, purpose, concession, circumstance. In English, adverbial clauses are separated by commas only when they come before the main clause.

Tense sentences combine the conjunction "so that" which is often replaced by "so" in spoken speech.

She sat behind me, so that (so) I couldn't see the expression of her face. He went to the lecture early so that (so) he got a good seat.

Subjunctive clauses. Subjunctive clauses show the condition despite the action of the main clause.

Although (although) it was only 9 o'clock, there were few people in the streets. He went out despite the fact that he had a bad cold.

Conditional clauses. Conditional clauses are connected with the main clause by the conjunctions if, unless, provided that, on condition (that), supposing (that).

He won't go there unless he is invited. "If I see him tomorrow, I shall ask him about this event".

Clauses of purpose. Clauses of purpose. shows the purpose of the action of the main sentence and what for? for what purpose? answers their questions. Clauses of purpose. is connected with the main clause by the conjunctions so that, so, in order that.

The teacher speaks slowly so that his pupils may understand him.

He drew a plan of the village so that she might be able to find his house easily.

The structure of any language depends on its internal laws. Languages do not use different grammatical devices in the same way due to their grammatical structure. The material basis of grammatical meaning and its source are grammatical means. Each grammatical meaning can only appear on the basis of grammatical means. Grammatical tools in world languages include suffixes, inflections, auxiliary words, pronouns, articles, supplementivism, etc. belongs to.

In English, grammatical devices such as articles, prepositions and auxiliary words play an important role in the speech process. Their formation occurs as a result of the language development process. These are grammatical devices specific to inflectional languages. In Azerbaijan, one of the agglutinative languages, case suffixes and postpositions are used instead of words.

Prepositions are at the beginning of a word and serve to create a subordinate relationship between words. In English, prepositions are used directly as creators of grammatical meanings. Semantically, prefixes in English correspond to case and postpositional suffixes in Azerbaijani

Transformation of language units is one of the most complex and urgent problems of translation theory. LS Barkhudarov approaches this problem as follows: "Translation unit" means that unit that is found in the speech text in the translated text, but may not correspond to its constituent parts in the separately translated text" [1, p. 257].

In modern linguistics, the hierarchy of language levels is distinguished by phonemes, morphemes, words, phrases, sentences and text. Language units in different languages of the system are also involved in translation at the same level.

Time branch clauses and branch clauses can be translated at the sentence and complex sentence level to preserve the semantics of the types of clause. At the same time, related to the internal rules of each language, different types of main and subordinate clauses, ways of closing appear in the form of sentences.

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